

Report on progress toward NextGEMS proposed links to IAMs

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Knowledge production will always be vital, but the unfolding of climate change, and the need to act, means that information provision has gained new urgency. An example that puts this more practically, is that for adapting regional water systems to a warming world it will be necessary to anticipate, and recognize, if summer rains over a given watershed will shift to winter rains. Understanding *why* this is happening won't always be possible (or even necessary) to guide action. These facts mean that demand to resolve questions of knowledge is taking a back seat to the demand for the provision of information, and means for verifying it.

The scientific gap that nextGEMS addresses is that the tools scientists developed to answer the big (academic) questions, as to whether Earth is warming and if humans are responsible, did not need regional accuracy and local granularity. This presumption has proven correct, as by now we understand the underlying processes responsible for this robustness in much simpler terms. A lack of regional fidelity, however, becomes a problem when one considers how to adapt to the regional manifestations of warming. Even if the regional fidelity of existing models were sufficient, the lack of local granularity means that whatever information that is provided, is difficult to translate into impacts and actions designed to mitigate against their negative manifestations. How can users interpret an extreme wind-storm if the models being used don't create such storms? In nextGEMS a new generation of models is being prototyped, models that not only have local granularity, but also offer the promise of regional fidelity, by demonstrating robust shifts in regional weather patterns. As society is increasingly confronted with the reality of climate change, it is looking to climate science to develop the tools needed to guide action and protect lives and livelihoods the world over, nextGEMS responds to this need.

In the beginning of nextGEMS we have pioneered novel workflows that are enabling a much broader community of users to interact with model output. This ranges from the mundane to the exotic. Agreement on standardized outputs and naming conventions for the two models, also in consultation with new users from the renewable energy sector and from marine biogeochemistry and fishery sector, is an example of the former. Exemplary of the latter is how output is being standardized on space-time hierarchical (HEALPix) grids that allow multi-resolution access, from data distributed using object stores and Zarr, and accessed through catalogues, to allow for efficient data management.

The importance of nextGEMS is highlighted by the forces it is helping set in motion. The Climate Adaptation Digital Twins of the Destination Earth project is being developed around the two prototype storm- and eddy-resolving (SR-ESMs) models being developed within nextGEMS. A large German National Project (WarmWorld) takes the nextGEMS development as its impetus for new workflows, and better blending of HPC and AI, to refactor and optimize the two models being developed in nextGEMS. Countless new EU projects are being based on the nextGEMS modeling capabilities. And in the first week of July 2023, a meeting is being held in Berlin, the Berlin Summit for EVE, that is exploring the development of multi-billion Euro infrastructures to support the use of models such as the ones developed in nextGEMS to form the basis of a new international climate information system.